

SUS-SOIL Project

SUS-SOIL is a project funded by the European Soil Mission that includes 22 partners from 13 countries and has a duration of 4 years. SUS-SOIL will develop 15 subsurface living labs (LLs) to inventory, analyse, and compare different land uses with agroecological soil management and their impact on the dynamics of the deep layers of arable soil (below 30 cm), with the aim of better combining agroecological management practices in rural and urban areas. The results of SUS-SOIL will serve as a starting point for land managers and public authorities to understand the risks associated with non-arable soil layers and to support the agroecological transformation of the European Union. SUS-SOIL will develop: (i) a subsurface monitoring database interoperable with LUCAS and ESDAC, (ii) long-term analysis of subsurface management in LLs taking into account different soil types, the provision of rural and urban ecosystem services, and modelling, (iii) a set of agricultural ideotypes that combine best agroecological management practices as an alternative to conventional systems, (iv) a decision-support tool for the subsurface and (v) a subsurface policy strategy framework to promote best agroecological management practices. It will also provide an algorithm for soil carbon storage rate in collaboration with the PEFC (Programme for the Endorsement of forest certification schemes).

Figure 1. SUS-SOIL Living Labs

AUTHORSHIP

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